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Spectrophotometric Determination of Ru(III) and Os(VIII) with 2,4,5-Triamino-6-Pyrimidinol

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Manuscript received 25 July 1978, revised 28 April 1980,
accepted 9 July 1980

IN continuation of the studies reported earlier from this laboratory¹⁻³ the use of 2,4,5-triamino-6-pyrimidinol⁴ for the colorimetric determination of Ru(III) and Os(VIII) is reported in this study.

Results and Discussion

Ruthenium : The broad experimental procedure for this work is as reported earlier⁵. Heating a 0.1 molar potassium chloride solution of a mixture of ruthenium (0.8-3 μg Ru/ml; the optimum concentration range from a Ringbom plot) and 60 fold amounts of the reagent adjusted to a pH range of 4.0-5.0 for 20 min on a water bath gave a violet red coloured solution with λ_{max} at 570 nm useful for the determination of ruthenium at the specified range of concentration. The Sandell's sensitivity of the system is 0.0036 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. From 8 aliquots of standard solution containing 1.98 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Ru, the standard deviation is 0.0050.

In determination of 2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of ruthenium the tolerance of other ions (conc. in $\mu\text{g/ml}$) is found to be as follows: Br^- , ClO_4^- , BO_3^{3-} , PO_4^{3-} (1000); F^- , I^- , NO_3^- , EDTA (200); tartrate, citrate, (100); Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} (400); Mg^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} (100); Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Zn^{2+} (60); Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+} (30); Sn^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Rh^{3+} , Ir^{3+} , Pt^{4+} and Os^{8+} (10). The presence of NO_2^- , CNS^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, thiourea, Ag^+ , Cu^{2+} and Au^{3+} causes interferences.

Osmium : The reaction with osmium in the optimum pH range of 7.0-8.5 is found to be instantaneous and is complete with 30 fold concentration of the reagent. The optimum range

of concentration is found to be 1.4-6.6 $\mu\text{g Os/ml}$ for the spectrophotometric determination at a λ_{max} of 490-500 nm. The Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction is 0.007 $\mu\text{g Os cm}^{-2}$. The standard deviation is 0.003 for 8 aliquots of standard solutions containing 4.7 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Os.

In the determination of 4.7 μg of Os/ml the tolerance of other ions (conc. in $\mu\text{g/ml}$) is found to be as follows: F^- , Br^- , CH_3COO^- , BO_3^{3-} , PO_4^{3-} (1000); I^- , NO_3^- , EDTA (500); CNS^- , citrate (250); Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Pb^{2+} (50); Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} ; Ru^{3+} (25); Mg^{2+} (20); Ag^+ , Sn^{2+} , Rh^{3+} , Ir^{3+} and Au^{3+} (5). In case of Zn, Cd, Mg and Sn, the absorbance was noted after centrifuging off the precipitated species: Hg^{2+} (50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) can co-exist in presence of 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of I^- . Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} (100) and Ni^{2+} (30) can be masked with EDTA and Co (30) with CNS^- . The presence of NO_2^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6^{2-}$, thiourea, Fe^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} causes serious interferences.

Of the substituted pyrimidines which have been developed for the spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium and osmium⁶⁻⁹, the present compound is the most sensitive but however is not of high selectivity. The solution of the reagent is not very stable and needs to be prepared fresh.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. G. R. Rao, IDPL, Hyderabad, for a gift sample of the ligand. One of us (P.J.) is also thankful to C.S.I.R. (New Delhi) for the award of Senior Research Fellowship.

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